

ARTISTIC INTERPRETATION OF SYMBOLIC IMAGES IN CHINGIZ AITMATOV'S NOVELS

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Abstract

In this article, figurative images in Chingiz Aitmatov's novels "Day of the Age", "Doomsday", "The Mark of Cassandra", "Mangu Qalliq" are analyzed.

Keywords

Image, figurative image, style, pictorial expression, animal, bird, plant symbols, idea, author's intention, artistic purpose, symbol, will, humanity,

We can see that Chingiz Aitmatov, an honored child of the Turkic people, who made a great contribution to the enrichment of the great source of spirituality of world literature with his masterpieces, skillfully used different images in the artistic development stages of his image creation. No matter what style, what visual means, an image is created, whether it is a human image, a historical person's image, a mythological image, or a metaphorical image, it is created according to the author's purpose, artistic intention, and interpretations of thought.

While thinking about the analysis and interpretation of artistic images in literary novels, in particular figurative (animal) images, first of all, we need to give some views on the concept of "image" in literary studies.

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According to the observations of literary studies, there are two ways to create an image:

- s 1) Creating an image by summation;
- 2) Creating an artistic image based on a prototype.

k The images created by this combination and prototype are divided into the following types according to their style and visual means:

- o 1) Fantasy images;
- w 2) Legendary images;

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¹Aristotle. Poetics (about the art of poetry). - T.: Gafur Ghulam Publishing House of Literature and Art, 1980. - p. 7,8,9.

† Hegel . Aesthetics . T. _ 4. M. , 1958. — 194.

‡ National encyclopedia of Uzbekistan. - T.: State scientific publishing house, 2003, 6 T. p. 439.

- 3) Mythological images;
- 4) Figurative (symbolic images);
- 5) Ironic images;
- 6) Satirical images;
- 7) Humorous images;

We see that Chingiz Aitmatov wisely used almost all of the images we mentioned above in his novels "The Day of the Century", "Doomsday", "The Mark of Cassandra", "Mangu Qalliq". For example: mythological figures Naiman mother, Jo'lamon in the novel "The Day of the Age", historical figure Hazrat Jesus in the novel "Doomsday", fantasy fiction (science fiction) Philofeus in "The Mark of Cassandra", metaphorical Jaabars in "Mangu Qaliq", etc. .

In this article, we tried to express our views on figurative images in the author's novels. In the writer's novel "A Day of the Century", we can see the fox, hawk, camel, dog, and fish from the figurative images. These images not only carry a certain meaning, but also help to understand the intended purpose of the work. The camel (Aqmoya, Karanor) in the novel "The Day of the Century" is a symbol of a whole history, continuity of generations, a fox is an example of views about the transformation of a certain animal, insect, or plant after a person's death. means Kazangap's death. The white bird flying out of Naiman's headscarf shouts "Donenbay", which is a symbol of the memory of human history and traditions. Universal groans in pain. And the fish is the child of Aedygeus and a symbol of his death. And the dog, as a symbol of loyalty, showed all his strength.

In the novel "Qiyamat" there is the following explanation about the origin of the name of the wolf Akbara and Toshchainar: "The wolf is Akdala among the local shepherds, but soon, according to information, he was assigned to Akbara, and then to Akbara the Great turned, but no one knew that this was a premonition. In the play, Toshchainar and Akbara appear as symbols of patience, strength, and power. In the subsequent events, motherhood and the spirit of perseverance that fought for survival really became Akbara's main virtues. The writer says that man is dehumanized, but this pair of wolves embodies high human qualities and our negative views about wolves . This is a pair of characters in the novel

In the second part of the novel "Doomsday", a lone bird - an eagle or a kite - flies in the hot sky for a long time and uniformly, represents the human will and desire for freedom and truth.

In the novel "Mangu Remnant", Jaabars became the king of the snowy mountains and lost his battle with the younger generation. Although he shows

his weakness and cannot hunt like before, he is independent and walks like a hermit in the mountains. The fate of Jaabars is to some extent connected with Arsene, who was striving for an ideal in art and died next to him.

In the novel "The Mark of Cassandra", the whales, throwing themselves on the shore of the ocean and killing themselves, stood as a target of injustices, evils and barbarities in the world.

Symbolic images that amaze people in the works of the writer were the heroes who served the principle of "Man deserves to be called a man", which became the creative motto of the writer. "Why are there so many images of animals in your works?" Chingiz Torakulovich said: "This is my nature, my way of perceiving the world. I do not describe man as separate from other creatures of the Creator. This method helps to complete the work and fill in the space, giving it meaning. I also love the Kremlin owl on the "Cassandra seal". Perhaps that bird is still living in the Kremlin towers, watching who comes at what time. His participation in the work is stronger than the traditional description of the event... Man is a being with a mind, he can create and destroy, bring good and oppress. The movement of animals is limited. They have become dependent on humans. "I will include them in the work so that people can understand how they should behave towards mute creatures," he said.

In short, the artistic image is of special importance in leading Chingiz Aitmatov to the original idea, purpose, and freshness of the work. We can taste the essence of spiritual perfection that sprouted from the bosom of the work, together with each image, each character, we taste their eternal dreams, fates, aspirations, characters, evolutions in their spiritual and spiritual world during the work. it is important for us to rejoice and grieve with them equally, and most importantly, to draw appropriate conclusions for ourselves. The theoretical basis of the image concept is a beacon that illuminates our distant path so that we can study the character, spiritual world, maturity, shortcomings, changes in the psyche of each character, the similar and different aspects of life paths and fates precisely on the typological plan. serves.

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